

DEVELOPMENT OF XF-2 FIGHTER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES (COCURED COMPOSITE WINGS)

Masami Kageyama¹ and Sinichi Yoshida²

¹ *Technical Research and Development Institute, Japan Defense Agency, Tokyo, Japan*

² *Nagoya Aerospace Systems, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Ltd. Nagoya, Japan*

SUMMARY: The structures of the XF-2 were based on the F-16, however, structural design of the XF-2 became an essentially new design, because of the change of structural materials such as high-strength composite materials. The drastic weight reduction of the XF-2 airframe was required to meet the high maneuverability 9G to -3G requirements. Composite materials are applied to wings, horizontal and vertical tails, some outer panels of center fuselage, and main and nose landing gear doors of the XF-2 fighters. High-strength composite materials accounted for about 18 percent of the total airframe structural weight. The weight of the wing structure was further reduced compared with conventional composite structures, because the lower skin, spars, and ribs of the XF-2 were co-cured applying the research of co-cured composite wing structures from the Technical Research and Development Institute of the Japan Defense Agency. Total weight reduction by using composite materials was estimated at about 250kg. Most of the full-scale airframe strength tests have been conducted. Some anomalies for co-cured composite wing structure have been found and modifications are reflected on the XF-2.

KEYWORDS : Fighter Structures, Composite Structures, Design and Testing

INTRODUCTION

The Japanese Next-Generation Support Fighter (XF-2), as the successor of the current support fighter (F-1), has been co-developed between Japan and the U.S. based on the USAF F-16 fighter aircraft, applying superior Japanese and U.S. technologies. The development of the XF-2 started in JFY 1988 and will be completed in JFY 2000. The main modifications made from F-16C to XF-2 are; larger wing area to improve turn performance, application of advanced materials and structural technology to reduce weight, installation of an improved performance engine to obtain better take off performance and to improve turn performance, application of radar absorption materials to improve stealth, and application of advanced avionics systems such as active-phased-array radar to improve the fire control performance. Six XF-2 prototype aircraft (two for full-scale airframe strength tests and four for flight tests) were manufactured as a result of the XF-2 design activities. The maiden flight was successfully carried out on October 7, 1995, and the company flight tests were also successfully

carried out. The government full-scale airframe strength tests (static and fatigue) have been scheduled from April 1995 to April 2000, and the government flight tests have been scheduled from March 1996 to June 2000.

The structures of the XF-2 were based on the F-16, however, structural design of the XF-2 became an essentially new design, because of the modification in airframe configuration such as about 25 percent increased wing area and increased number of under-wing hard points, and the change of structural materials such as high-strength composite materials. The strength analysis was conducted based on the results of the wind tunnel tests and the design criteria for the XF-2. The structural design progressed according to the results of basic material tests (such as coupon tests), structure element (such as wing spars) tests, sub-structure (such as wing-fuselage joint portions) tests and full-scale component tests such as wings under environmental conditions. ASIP (Aircraft Structural Integrity Program) was applied to the XF-2 from the early phase of design.

STRUCTURAL DESIGN CRITERIA

Basic requirements for the XF-2 structural design were fixed in the XF-2 structural design criteria. Basic concept on the XF-2 structural design requirements was based on the series of MIL-A-008860, similar to the F-16. The XF-2 has high maneuverability under load factors of 9G to -3G under the light-weight configuration with two air-to-air short range missiles. The XF-2, even under heavy-weight configuration with four air-to-ship missiles, can maneuver at maximum load factor. Also, the OWS (Over-load Warning System) was installed in the XF-2 in order to inform the pilot of acceptable load factor and warn when the limit is approaching.

The damage tolerance design was applied to the flight safety structures. For example, thick composite structures were certified by conducting strength tests after 40 feet-lb impacts.

MATERIALS APPLIED TO XF-2

The drastic weight reduction of the XF-2 airframe was required, to meet the high maneuverability 9G to -3G requirements. High-strength composite materials, as shown in Table 1, accounted for about 18 percent (710kg) of the total airframe structural weight. Table 2 shows ratios of materials applied to the XF-2. Weight reductions were estimated at about 250kg. Especially, the weight of the wing structure was further reduced compared with conventional composite structures, because the lower skin, spars, and ribs of the XF-2 were co-cured applying the research of co-cured composite wing structures from the Third Research Center of TRDI, JDA.¹ Composite materials are applied to wings, horizontal and vertical tails, some outer panels of center fuselage, and main and nose landing gear doors of the XF-2 fighters as shown in Fig. 1. In order to certify that composite materials could be applied to the XF-2, development tests for composite materials, as mentioned in the next section, were conducted.

Fig. 1 Composite material application.

Table 1 Characteristics of composite materials.

	XF-2 Composites	Conventional Composites
Fiber Elasticity	30 ton/mm ²	25 ton/mm ²
Fiber Strength	500 kg/mm ²	300 kg/mm ²

Table 2 Material application ratio.

Composite Materials	18%
Aluminum Alloy	61%
Titanium Alloy	8%
Steel Alloy	3%
Others	10%

OUTLINE OF AIRFRAME STRUCTURES

The XF-2 airframe is composed of wings, horizontal tails, vertical tail, fuselage and ventral fins. Fig. 2 shows the basic components of the XF-2 airframe structures.

Fig. 2 Airframe components.

The XF-2 wings are increased by 25% in area compared to that of the F-16 wings and have a lot of structural changes from the F-16. The XF-2 wing structures are made of wing box structure attached by leading edge flap, trailing edge flaperon and fixed trailing edge. Wings are jointed to bulkheads of central fuselage, by using five pairs of tension attachments in upper and lower skins respectively, and two pairs of shear attachments on front and rear spars. As for the wing box structure, lower skin, spars, and ribs of the XF-2 are co-cured by using high-strength composite materials. High-strength composite materials are also applied to the upper skin of wing box and skins of flaperon and fixed trailing edge. The inside of the wing box is used as an integral fuel tank. Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show configuration and manufacturing process of the XF-2 co-cured composite wing box, respectively. The XF-2 leading edge flaps are used as maneuver flaps, therefore the angles of the leading edge flaps are frequently changed. The XF-2 leading edge flaps consist of inboard and outboard components, which are joined at split. This split mechanism, which allows span-wise motion, was adopted to minimize the wing/flap interaction loads during severe wing bending situation.

Fig.3 Wing box configuration.

Fig.4 Manufacturing process of co-cured composite wings.

Although the horizontal tails of the XF-2 are larger by 20 percent than those of the F-16, their structures are similar to those of the F-16. The XF-2 horizontal tail is composed of upper and lower composite skins, waved aluminum spar, and full depth honeycomb leading edge, and jointed to aft fuselage by β -titanium pivot shaft. The XF-2 vertical tail consists of a box structure (composed of skins, spars, and ribs), leading edge portion, and rudder. The rudder is a full-depth honeycomb structure, and is attached to the vertical tail box by using hinges. The vertical tail is jointed to the aft fuselage by using three pairs of tension attachments. High-strength composite materials are applied to skins of the vertical tail including rudder.

The XF-2 fuselage consists of forward, center and aft fuselages, and speed brakes and ventral fins are attached to the aft fuselage. The forward fuselage structure is a multi-frame structure with several longerons. The windshield attached to the forward fuselage is a reinforced windshield considering bird strikes. The center fuselage is a thick-skin multi-frame structure, proper to fuel tanks, and the upper part of fuel tank has several inspection panels. High-strength composite materials are applied to several upper panels of the center fuselage and doors of nose and main landing gears. The forward part of the aft fuselage is a fuel tank structure and the aft part is a structure to support horizontal and vertical tails. The forward and center fuselages are joined by skins and inlet duct longerons, and the center and aft fuselage are jointed by skins, inner skin of engine room, and keel beam. When composite structures of aircraft are struck by lightning during their flight, such composite structures could be damaged by the heat due to lightning electric current compared to conventional metal structures. Therefore, thin aluminum meshes are bonded to the surface of composite structures of the XF-2 fighters in order to lead the lightning electric current directly to metal structures.

Development Tests for Composite Materials

Static strength, durability, and damage tolerance were considered for strength requirements to be on the XF-2 composite structures, and requirements to each strength on the XF-2 composite structures are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Requirements for composite structures,

Static Strength	Harmful deformation or permanent deformation shall not occurred at LMT load. Endure Ultimate load(150% LMT)
Durability Strength	Endure one design life loading without damages induced by corrosion, thermal and humidity. Endure one design life loading without hole wear induced by repeat loading
Damage Tolerance Strength	Shall not fail through two life loading, and shall satisfy the residual strength requirements : 110%LMT load, even if prescribed manufacturing defects exist. Satisfy the residual strength requirement : 100%LMT load even if operation damage *) existed.

Note *) Operation Damage . Damage caused by any tool drop or small object impact during aircraft operations

To apply high-strength composite materials to the XF-2 airframe structures, strength tests and

strength evaluation were conducted step-by-step from basic material characteristics to full-scale structures, and the results were reflected to the XF-2 structural design. Test cases and their objectives of the XF-2 composite structural tests and test schedule are shown in Table 4 and 5, respectively.

Table 4 Items and purposes of development tests for composite materials.

Test Item	Test Porpoise	Test Articles
Basic Material Tests	-Acquisition of strength/stiffness data -Acquisition of joint durability data -Acquisition of strength effect of manufacturing defects (delamination and voids) -Acquisition of strength effect of impact damage	Test Items ; 6 Items Test specimen ; About 1900
Structure Element Tests	-Acquisition of productivity and strength characteristics -Acquisition of environmental effects and capability of inspection for manufacturing defects on composite structure	Test Items : 9 Items Test specimen ; About 400
Sub-Structure Tests	-Confirm static strength, durability and damage tolerance requirement for major sub-structure -Confirm repair methods and strength after repair for major sub-structure -Confirm strength effect against prescribed operational damage	Test Items ; 10 Items Test specimen ; About 230
Full-scale Component Tests	-Confirm durability and residual strength after operational damage under environmental(temperature and humidity) condition	Test Items ; 4 Items Test specimen ; 5

Table 5 Schedule of development tests for composite materials.

TEST	YEAR							
	JFY1990	JFY1991	JFY1992	JFY1993	JFY1994	JFY1995	JFY1996	
BASIC MATERIAL TEST	[Bar]							
STRUCTURE ELEMENT TEST	[Bar]							
SUB-STRUCTURE TEST		[Bar]						
FULL-SCALE COMPONENT TEST				[Bar]				
DESIGN PHASE (reference)	CONCEPT DRAWING	LAYOUT DRAWING	DETAILED LAYOUT DRAWING	PRODUCTION DRAWING		FULL SCALE STATIC/DURABILITY TEST		

BASIC MATERIAL TESTS

To apply high-strength composite materials to the XF-2 airframe structures, basic data such as material mechanical characteristics and environmental characteristics of high-strength composite materials were acquired by basic material tests and the test results were reflected on design allowable. Coupon tests on lmina property, fastener joint property, and etc. were conducted. The outline of basic material tests is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Basic material tests.

STRUCTURE ELEMENT TESTS

The objectives of structure element tests are to acquire data regarding manufacturing process and strength of main structure element among parts of wing, tail, and fuselage structures applied composite materials, and to acquire data regarding environmental effect on strength and non-destructive inspection of defect including delamination and void during manufacturing. Strength characteristics of primary composite structures were evaluated by these structure element tests, and thereby design data were acquired. The outline of basic material tests is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.6 Structure element tests.

SUB-STRUCTURE TESTS

As for wing, tail, and fuselage structures applied high-strength composite materials, sub-structure test articles simulated to structural critical parts were fabricated. Static strength, durability, and damage tolerance data were acquired by conducting sub-structure tests, and structural design of these structures applied composite materials was evaluated. Structural critical parts were quite important in flight safety such as wing-fuselage joints and leading edge flap attachments, and were applied complicated flight loads such as loads from fastener joints as well as tension / compression loads. As for flaperon, horizontal tail, and rudder structures, sub-structures, simulated to complicated load path parts such as structures around pivot shafts, were tested. Primary structures such as wing-fuselage joints after remedy were also tested to establish remedy methods and acquire strength after remedy. The outline of basic material tests is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig.7 Sub-structure tests.

FULL-SCALE COMPONENT TESTS

As for co-cured composite structures such as wing box structures and bonded composite structures such as flaperon, durability tests of full-scale component test articles were conducted under actual mission load and environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, and residual strength tests of these test articles after mission damage. Thereby, durability and damage tolerance after damage applied during missions of these structures under environmental conditions was evaluated. The outline of basic material tests is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Full-scale component tests.

GOVERNMENT FULL-SCALE AIRFRAME STRENGTH TESTS

The government full-scale airframe strength tests of the XF-2 consisted of full-scale airframe static test and full-scale airframe fatigue test. The full-scale airframe static strength test had approximately 140 test cases including symmetrical pull-up loads, rolling pull-out loads, 1G roll loads and external store loads. It started in April 1995, and all of test cases were completed in June 2000. The full-scale airframe fatigue test was composed of durability and damage tolerance tests. The flight-by-flight loading pattern was applied in these tests, simulating flight, landing, and ground loads, cockpit and fuel tank pressure, and engine thrust loads. The full-scale airframe durability test started in November 1995, and two lives of design load spectrum and inspections were completed in July 1997. The full-scale airframe damage tolerance test and tear-down inspection after all loadings had been completed during the period from January 1998 to March 1999.

Some anomalies for the XF-2 structures, such as lack of strength around fuel holes on ribs and around holes on the lower skin of co-cured composite wing structures, and around the co-cured composite wing portion attached to flaperon, had been found in the government full-scale airframe strength tests and modifications are reflected to the XF-2 aircraft. The lack of strength around fuel holes on ribs of co-cured composite wing structures was occurred due to stress concentration around these holes, and metal attachments as improvement were applied such ribs. The lack of strength around holes on the lower skin of co-cured composite wing structures was also resulted from stress concentration around these holes, so shapes of such holes were modified and thick of composite lower skin around such holes would be increased as improvement. The lack of strength around the co-cured composite wing portion attached to flaperon was occurred due to delamination between the lower skin and spar/rib, and modification of radius blocks and fasteners were applied. During the full-scale

airframe fatigue strength test, no major anomalies occurred.

CONCLUSION

The XF-2 Structures had been developed according to newly development steps, although they were developed based on the USAF F-16. These valuable experiences would be linked to future projects. Composite materials were first in Japan applied to the primary structures of airframe such as wings. The XF-2 co-cured composite wing technology had been transferred to the United States as Japanese advanced technology.

REFERENCES

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